

Digital showcase of integration of CeOS in HE Curricula in SE Europe

ABSTRACT

This document is a summary of the aims, scope, methodology and outputs that guided the delivery of eight publicly available videos (digital showcase) with faculty members of Library and Information Science departments in Europe.

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Consortium

Organisation	Country	Author
Stichting LIBER	The Netherlands	Project Coordinator
Syddansk Universitet	Denmark	Partner
Universita Defli Studi Di Torino	Italy	Partner
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Aim and scope

The aim of this section is to present the results of the PR5A2 activity which is a digital showcase of short videos. Through these interviews, we have explored the obstacles in CeOS uptake or the adoption of good practices in CeOS in Higher Education curricula and teaching practices. It was paramount to show both sides of the situation, i.e. difficulties or challenges on one hand, and practices of uptake on the other.

Methodology

UP, the leader of this PR, with the help of the project partners, identified several faculty members to be interviewed. Following this, a list of questions was developed and shared with the project partners. The project partners had the liberty to rearrange the order of the questions as suited during the interview.

They were asked to fix some virtual meetings to conduct the interviews. Most of these were taken remotely, as it was deemed right to avoid travel within the same country to minimize the carbon footprint of the project.

A form was prepared and distributed to the respondents, to have their consent for use and dissemination of the videos. Where the consent was not secured, the videos were not uploaded. However, their opinions were studied to gather as much information as possible.

Outputs

The outputs can be found on YouTube, on the [channel](#) of the CeOS_SE project. More specifically, on the [playlist](#) titled “Digital showcase of integration of Citizen-Enhanced Open Science in Higher Education curricula in Southeastern Europe”.

Acknowledgement

UP would like to thank all project partners for their effort in taking the interviews. We would also like to thank the respondents for providing substantial information to understand the integration of Citizen Science in the Library and Information Science curricula.

Appendix 1 - Interview Questions

- Would you like to introduce yourselves? Can you tell us a little about your department, your area of expertise and the courses that you teach?
- Do you teach topics of Open Science and what is your knowledge about Citizen Science?
- How do you think Citizen Science is connected to the Library and Information Science studies?
- Have you ever used concepts and practices of Citizen Science as part of your curriculum? If so, how did you use them and what is your experience? If not, would you ever consider using Citizen Science in your curriculum?
- Would you consider Citizen Science a standalone course or part of another, broader, course?
- What are the skills that you would deem necessary for someone to have in order to teach Citizen Science as part of the curriculum? Does the Faculty staff have the skills to make that possible?
- Do you believe that Citizen Science is a topic that requires practice on the field of work?
- What more do you think needs to happen for it to become applicable in the long term and sustainable?
- Have you ever participated in a Citizen Science activity? If yes, what was the activity? If not, would you be interested in participating in one, and what would be your ideal Citizen Science project?

Appendix 2 - Interview Consent Form

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview for the purposes of the CeOS_SE project. Ethical procedures require that interviewees explicitly understand the purpose of the study and the intended use of their contribution and provide their consent.

Please read the accompanying information and sign this form confirming that you understand and approve the following points:

- Your participation in this project is voluntary and you can withdraw whenever you want.
- You do not expect any compensation whatsoever.
- The interview will be recorded, and a file can be available to have access to and, if deemed necessary, to propose edits to ensure that the confidentiality of your contribution is intact.
- Access to the interview file (and to any possible by-product, such as a transcript) will be limited to the research team of University of Patras and academic colleagues and researchers with whom they might collaborate as part of the research process, who then will analyse and extract material.
- Preservation of the interview file will be in accordance with the standards that are required by the project management and the compliance of the CeOS_SE project with EU regulations. Anonymized by-products, such as a transcript, may be stored on public repositories or websites and may be reused under the CC-BY licence.
- Your interview (in whole or in part, in the form of quotes) may be used in scholarly papers, conference presentations, project documents and reports, and/or media articles; this will be anonymized, and you will not be identifiable in any of it.

Please note that our research team will be available to answer any questions that came up before and after the interview and will be available to contact in case you have questions in the future.

Detailed information about the project CeOS_SE is available at the [CeOs Project Website](#).

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Participant's Name and Signature:

Date:

Researcher's Name and Signature:

Date:

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Appendix 3 - Interview set up guide

Equipment needed

- The interview can be conducted by digital camera, smartphone or a web application, such as StreamYard.
- Minimum resolution: 1280x720
- Export file formats: MP4
- All files can be uploaded on the designated GDrive folder.
- All interviewees will have the questions in advance, at least one week earlier, so that there is enough time to prepare their answers.
- All interviewees will have the data consent form in advance. we will need the signing on the document or its recording before the answers.
- If the interviewee does not speak English, then we will request from the local teams to transcribe their replies in order to provide captions.
- If possible, do record the interviews on a phone too, so that we have the audio file as a separate file. The sound will be clearer on a recording in case the video audio is not good.

On site

- We recommend the use of two cameras (or smartphones). One to be placed in front of the interviewee and one on the side showing the interviewee's profile at a 45o corner.
- The interviewer will ask the question, but he/she will not be shown. Please make sure that the question is being asked as clearly as possible for visually impaired persons. Please ask the interviewee to respond accordingly.

Remotely

- The app that will be used for the remote interviews is StreamYard.

- Streamyard is an online platform so there is no need to download/install anything.
- A camera and a microphone is necessary.
- Theodora has to be present to record the interview.
- The interview will be conducted by the partner.
- Set up a date for the interviews.
- After the confirmation of the date, a link will be sent out for the interview and everyone will connect through that link.

Space set up

- Preferably in an office/library setting. Collaboration spaces in the background are also welcomed.
- Quite space/As little noise as possible
- There should be no sun behind the interviewee.
- The camera(s) should be placed so as to at least one camera shows the interviewee's profile on the side.
- The microphone (be that on the phone or a separate one) should be elevated and close to the mouth of the interviewee.

